

Effects of Ultraviolet Radiation on Amino Acid Composition of Single Cell Protein

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Effects of ultraviolet radiation upon the viability and amino acid composition of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Candida utilis*, used for single-cell protein (SCP) production, have been studied. A slight difference in the radiation resistance of the two species was found. Radiation doses up to 75 sec seemed to have marginal degrading effect on the various amino acids present in the SCP products. The contents of protein was also not significantly changed.

A review of literature shows that only a few attempts have been made to study the effects of radiation on the preservation of single-cell protein (SCP)¹⁻⁵. One important requirement for microorganisms selected for SCP production from various substrates is that of non-pathogenicity. The heating to which the product is subjected during processing should be strong enough to kill a substantial fraction of the viable cells. Intense heat may, however, affect various nutritional components of the SCP products. It is, therefore, necessary that sterilization processes should be considered carefully, either without or in combination with heat treatment.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to study the effects of ultraviolet radiation upon the viability of cells and amino acid composition of the SCP products of two microbial strains, namely *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Candida utilis*, used for SCP production.

Experimental

Materials and Methods :

Microorganisms and medium : The organisms *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Candida utilis* were procured from the Department of Botany, University of Allahabad, Allahabad. These cultures were maintained by monthly transfer on glucose-yeast extract agar medium and were stored at low temperature for further use.

For irradiation, the organisms were grown in 2% glucose-yeast extract-peptone water (YP water) for 72 hr at 30°. 10 ml of the cell containing material (approximately 10⁷ cells/ml) were pipetted into a sterilized petridish and irradiated with the lid of the dish removed. The viability of the cells, of the non-irradiated controls kept at ambient temperature, and of the irradiated samples, was examined by the surface count method using Sabouraud's agar and incubation for 48 hr at 30°.

Irradiation : For irradiating the microorganisms, a UV lamp (Cat. No. CM 03106 ser. N 0232, Toshniwal, India) was used. The wavelength range

of the source was 3900-4300 Å. The samples (1.0 g/l biomass) were placed at fixed distance (30 cm) from the source and doses were varied in respect of time. Thus, the cell suspensions were irradiated for 15, 30, 45, 60 and 75 sec.

The crude protein was estimated by the method of MacKenzie and Wallace⁶. The amino acid analysis of the protein was done with a Beckman Model 116 amino acid analyser (operated according to principles described by Spackman *et al.*⁷) after hydrolysis according to the method of Weidner and Eggvin⁸.

Results and Discussion

The inactivation of cells of *S. cerevisiae* and *C. utilis*, when irradiated with ultraviolet rays is shown in Figs. 1 and 2. It is seen from the figures that a successive decrease occurred in the survival pattern of the cells with increase in the dose of irradiation.

Fig. 1

Protein content : The total protein content of irradiated and non-irradiated samples are recorded in Table 1. Tables 2 and 3 show the effect of

Fig. 2

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF PROTEIN CONTENTS OF NON-IRRADIATED AND IRRADIATED CELLS OF *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* AND *Candida utilis*

Organism	Total protein content of dry cell mass (%)					
	Non-irradiated	Irradiated (time in sec)				
		15	30	45	60	75
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	45.5	45.2	45.1	44.8	45.0	44.7
<i>C. utilis</i>	45.0	45.0	44.8	44.6	44.7	44.6

TABLE 2—AMINO ACID COMPOSITION OF NON-IRRADIATED AND IRRADIATED SCP PRODUCTS OF *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (g/16 g N)

Amino acids	Non-irradiated	Irradiation dose (sec)					
		15	30	45	60	75	
Essential amino acids	Lysine	8.30	7.70	7.61	7.20	7.00	6.85
	Threonine	7.65	7.90	7.88	7.69	7.50	7.01
	Valine	6.97	7.86	7.62	7.18	6.95	7.13
	Methionine	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Isoleucine	6.41	7.00	7.29	7.41	7.41	7.49
	Phenylalanine	5.15	5.71	6.43	5.32	5.43	4.89
	Tryptophan	—	—	—	—	—	—
Non-essential amino acids	Alanine	8.87	8.99	8.78	9.00	7.77	8.30
	Arginine	4.98	5.25	4.91	4.39	5.10	5.00
	Aspartic acid	14.93	15.00	14.57	14.50	14.30	14.42
	Cysteine	1.72	1.74	1.70	1.78	1.73	1.80
	Glutamic acid	14.69	14.92	14.71	15.30	14.71	15.00
	Glycine	5.88	6.63	5.87	6.37	5.78	6.06
	Histidine	1.58	2.40	1.90	1.73	1.89	1.98
	Proline	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Serine	6.67	7.00	6.37	6.25	5.82	5.84
Tyrosine	1.74	2.00	1.75	1.80	1.97	1.72	

irradiation on amino acids in SCP products of *S. cerevisiae* and *C. utilis*. Methionine, proline and tryptophan could not be detected with the analytical method used. No nutritional evaluations was done.

TABLE 3—AMINO ACID COMPOSITION OF NON-IRRADIATED AND IRRADIATED SCP PRODUCTS OF *Candida utilis* (g/16 g N)

Amino acids	Non-irradiated	Irradiation dose (sec)					
		15	30	45	60	75	
Essential amino acids	Lysine	6.86	7.85	6.66	7.52	6.42	7.19
	Threonine	5.36	5.40	5.90	5.94	5.81	6.43
	Valine	5.66	6.18	7.75	4.43	5.81	5.61
	Methionine	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Isoleucine	5.50	5.37	5.30	4.41	4.57	5.65
	Phenylalanine	4.20	3.36	4.08	3.70	3.59	3.10
	Tryptophan	—	—	—	—	—	—
Non-essential amino acids	Alanine	7.71	8.00	7.42	8.03	7.78	8.03
	Arginine	5.00	4.93	4.77	4.00	4.31	4.53
	Aspartic acid	13.00	12.00	11.00	10.58	11.82	11.42
	Crysteine	1.35	1.30	1.36	1.36	1.30	1.31
	Glutamic acid	20.12	19.63	19.61	24.01	22.18	22.11
	Glycine	4.83	4.61	5.21	5.23	5.29	5.26
	Histidine	2.38	2.98	2.89	2.67	2.63	2.32
	Proline	—	—	—	—	—	—
	Serine	7.18	7.02	5.98	6.77	5.78	6.08
	Tyrosine	3.08	3.12	3.45	3.44	3.46	2.99

It is seen that in both the cases destruction of amino acids increased with increase in irradiation time, and total protein content of irradiated samples was less than that of non-irradiated products. Lysine content of *S. cerevisiae* decreased slightly on 15 sec irradiation dose, but it increased in case of *C. utilis*.

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